

ACCIDENT PREVENTION AND DETECTION SYSTEM USING IOT

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Abstract

Road safety is a huge issue all over the world as there are rising numbers of road accidents, most of which are caused by driving while intoxicated. To counteract this, we introduce a smart alcohol detection system that improves road safety by barring drivers from driving after consumption of alcohol. The system consists of several components such as an alcohol sensor, Arduino microcontroller, GPS, GSM, and engine locking mechanism. The alcohol sensor continuously tracks the driver's breath for alcohol content. When the alcohol content is found to be above the acceptable level, the system automatically locks the engine, and the vehicle cannot start or continue running. The GPS module transmits real-time location information, and the GSM module alerts specified contacts, such as the vehicle owner or authorities, with an emergency message, allowing timely action. The system also features a buzzer that notifies the driver and surrounding people when alcohol is present, and an LCD screen for displaying information. Various versions of the system incorporate sensors for detecting driver fatigue, vibration sensors for crash detection, and heart rate sensors to enhance safety. Wireless communication and real-time monitoring make this system versatile for both pre- and post-crash situations.

Keywords: - Alcohol detection, GSM, GPS, Engine locking, Arduino, Drunk driving prevention, Embedded system, Real-time monitoring, Road safety

1. INTRODUCTION

Road safety is a critical worldwide concern, with road traffic accidents causing a significant number of injuries and fatalities annually. As reported by the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 1.35 million individuals lose their lives every year in road traffic accidents, with an even higher number sustaining serious injuries. Drowsy driving is responsible for approximately 20% of these occurrences, with alcohol-impaired driving taking a considerable proportion as well. In the United States, for instance, the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) cited that alcohol impaired driving results in over 10,000 fatalities annually. These alarming statistics reflect the urgent necessity for better safety measures to prevent driver-related crashes, while conventional strategies such as awareness campaigns and legal regulations have failed to reduce fatalities.

In order to address this problem, the intended project aims to develop an automated real-time safety system that utilizes current technologies like computer vision, alcohol sensors, and the Internet of Things (IoT). The gadget will utilize face recognition to identify signs of driver fatigue and alcohol sensors to track blood alcohol levels. Once the system identifies alcohol or fatigue impairment, it immediately warns the driver and refuses to allow the car to start or keep running. Furthermore, GSM technology

will also be used to send real-time warnings to the authorities or emergency numbers so that action can be taken immediately. By taking preventative measures against driver impairment before it leads to an accident, this proactive system is designed to significantly lower road fatalities and enhance overall road safety.

Problem Statement

Drunken or drowsy driving is one of the major causes of traffic accidents and deaths globally. Even with a wide range of preventive measures, ranging from legislative restrictions to public safety campaigns, accidents due to drunk or drowsy driving are alarmingly high.

Existing systems based solely on human judgment are often unreliable as drivers might be unaware of their impairment or prefer to ignore it. Consequently, there is a critical need for an automated system that can sense and evaluate the state of the driver in real time and initiate the necessary measures to avoid hazardous driving. This project attempts to solve this problem by developing a system that detects driver fatigue and alcohol consumption and ensures warnings are sent and prevents the vehicle from operating in dangerous conditions, hence minimizing the likelihood of road accidents.

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Objective

The aim of the project is to design an extensive driver safety monitoring system that comprises alcohol detection, drowsiness monitoring, and accident detection. It identifies alcohol content and signs of fatigue and immobilizes the car engine in case of impairment. Also, the system will identify accidents and send real-time notifications with GPS coordinates to emergency contacts through GSM technology. This combined approach enhances road safety, reduces accident rates, and delivers rapid assistance in times of crisis, while enhancing driver awareness through real-time feedback.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Driver Drowsiness Detection System

Authors: Sai Krishna Paruchuri, Daniel Paul

This research discusses an Arduino-based system for identifying driver drowsiness using IR sensors, cameras, and accelerometers. It aims at tracking eye closure frequency and yawning as indicators of drowsiness, with the alert signaled through a buzzer or vibration system. The authors propose future enhancement in the form of integration with vehicle controls for automated safety measures.

A Review Paper on Pre and Post Accident Detection and Alert System: An IoT Application for Complete Safety of the Vehicles

Authors: Vaishali Shrivastava, Manasi Gyanchandani

This article explores IoT-based technologies for safety in vehicles with emphasis on pre- and post-accident detection. It discusses the functions of accelerometers, gyroscopes, GPS, and GSM modules in accident detection and emphasizes the importance of sensor fusion to increase detection accuracy.

Accident Detection and Monitoring System Using IoT

Authors: Dr. D. Karunkuzhali, D. Madhubala, Y. Nisha, S. Rajeswari.

This paper outlines an IoT-based real-time crash detection system using accelerometers, GPS modules, and GSM modules. It emphasizes precise crash detection and instant location-based notification to enhance emergency response times.

A Comprehensive Study on IoT-Based Accident Detection Systems for Smart Vehicles

Authors: Unaiza Alvi, Muazzam A. Khan Khattak, Balawal Shabir, Asad Waqar Malik, Sher Ramzan Muhammad.

This paper compares different IoT-based accident detection systems for intelligent vehicles, including technologies like accelerometers and gyroscopes. The research focuses on real-time tracking and cloud data management to improve vehicle safety and accident response.

Vehicle Tracking and Alcohol Detector with Engine Locking System with GSM and GPS

Authors: M. Navya Sri, N. Saritha, N. Navya, Dr.N. Jagadeeshan.

This paper discusses a car tracking system with a built-in alcohol sensor and engine lock system. It targets real-time tracking and engine locking in case of alcohol detection, improving vehicle security and safety

Review Paper on Alcohol Detection and Vehicle Engine Locking System

Authors: Dr. K. Ravi Kumar, Yellapu Neeraj Kumar, Midathana Kisran, Urikiti Teja, MD Shakeer.

The paper discusses an alcohol detection system wired to an automobile's ignition, inhibiting engine activation upon the detection of excessive alcohol. The system combines GPS and GSM to enhance protection by informing emergency contacts in the event of alcohol detection.

Alcohol Detection and Engine Locking System

Authors: Nookala Venu, Vamshi M, Akhil V, Deepika K, Prashanth K, Raffiudhin M

This research presents an alcohol detection system with an engine lock capability, powered by a microcontroller Arduino, and real-time alerts to emergency contacts over GSM. It recommends additional safety features via integration of accident detection.

Alcohol Detection with Automatic Engine Locking System

Authors: P. Sree Lekha, Dr. P. Venkata Prasad.

This article outlines a system that employs MQ-3 alcohol sensors with vehicle ignition to immobilize operation upon detection of high alcohol levels. It focuses on reliability in alcohol detection and automatic engine immobilization, which leads to road safety.

Design & Development of Arduino-based Alcohol Sensing and Dizziness Detecting Braking System

Authors: Md. Naimur Asif Borno, Prangon Das, Md. Touhid Islam, Mushfique Ahmed, Azim Miah, Nadia Kachmina

This research investigates a system that combines alcohol detection with automatic braking based on motion and alcohol sensors. The system is under the control of an Arduino with the aim of detecting dizziness or intoxication and deploying brakes as a precautionary measure. Future development will see this system augmented with other safety technologies.

System Architecture

The architecture of the system of this accident detection and prevention project using IoT is composed of various components and sensors to ensure the safety of drivers and provide real-time alerts during emergencies. Its core is the Arduino UNO microcontroller, serving as the processor, aggregating and processing information from an assortment of sensors such as an accident detection pressure sensor. The power supply component ensures that every component has stable power during use.

The system comprises a sleepiness detection module based on an infrared sensor to monitor the driver's eyes and head movements for signs of drowsiness. An alcohol detection sensor (MQ-3) scans the driver's breath for signs of alcohol consumption. When either of these sensors

identifies impairment, the system emits a buzzer to alert the driver, and the motor driver kills the vehicle's engine to stop further movement.

In case of a crash, the pressure sensor identifies sudden impacts on the vehicle and transmits signals to the Arduino, which then triggers the accident response. The GSM module quickly sends SMS alerts to pre-programmed emergency numbers, such as critical details like accident detection and vehicle location, which is monitored by the GPS module. Real-time communication enhances emergency response by providing instant information regarding the location and severity of the accident.

Arduino UNO (Microcontroller)

Role: The Arduino UNO analyzes sensor data and carries out programmed decisions.

Responsibilities:

- Collects sensor data (alcohol, drowsiness, accidents).
- Executes algorithms to gauge the condition of the driver and the vehicle status.
- Initiates responses such as SMS notification, engine control, and activation of the buzzer.

3. SENSORS

Drowsiness Detection Module:

Type: IR Sensor

Function: It monitors the eye movement of the driver through infrared reflection to identify closed eyes or low rates of blinking.

Alcohol Detection Sensor:

Type: Alcohol gas sensor.

Function: Measures BAC by sensing alcohol vapor in the driver's breath.

Accident Detection Sensor:

Type: ADXL345 (Accelerometer Sensor)

Function: Senses sudden acceleration changes or impact by sensing acceleration in X, Y, and Z axes.

4. GSM MODULE

Type: GSM SIM900A or similar.

Function: Sends SMS notifications to emergency contacts during accidents or system faults

GPS Module

Type: GPS Module (e.g., NEO-6M).

Function: Traces the location of the vehicle, especially useful during accidents.

Buzzer:

Type: Piezoelectric buzzer.

Function: Gives an audible alert when alcohol or drowsiness is detected.

Motor Driver and Vehicle Engine Control: Type: Motor driver IC (e.g., L298N).

Function: Controls the vehicle engine's state according to sensor input.

Power Supply:

Type: 12V DC power supply or battery.

Function: Supplies power to the microcontroller, sensors, and communication modules.

5. CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Figure 1 Circuit Diagram of Accident Prevention and Detection System Using IOT

Testing & Results

Types of Testing Conducted

- Unit Testing: Tested every module separately (e.g., alcohol sensor, vibration sensor, GPS module, GSM module).
- Integration Testing: Verified how modules interact with each other in the IoT system.
- System Testing: Simulated real-world scenarios to verify how the entire system performs during an accident or when alcohol is present.

Results

Table 1 Results

Test Case	Scenario	Expected Output	Actual Result	Status
TC01	Seat belt detected	Engine should start normally	Engine started	Passed
TC02	Seat belt not detected	Engine should not start	Engine locked	Passed
TC03	Alcohol detected	Engine should not start	Engine locked	Passed
TC04	No alcohol detected	Engine should start normally	Engine started	Passed
TC05	Drowsiness detected	Engine should not start	Engine locked	Passed
TC06	Drowsiness not detected	Engine should start normally	Engine started	Passed
TC07	Sudden impact/acceleration detected	Alert SMS sent with GPS location	SMS received	Passed

6. CONCLUSION

The Accident Prevention and Detection System using alcohol, drowsiness, and accident detection technology is a preventive measure for ensuring road safety. The system

detects the state of the driver and the status of the car in real time through the integration of sensors, GSM and GPS modules, and IoT features. This automated technology not only avoids impaired driving by shutting down the car's engine, but it also offers a rapid response mechanism during accidents through location-based alerts. The system is a major upgrade in road safety technology since it can reduce accident rates and allow for faster emergency responses. In the coming times, the system can be supplemented with new functionalities like monitoring one's health and environmental factors so that the roads become safe for all.

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